

Promotion Strategy of Local Artisan-Made Product

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ABSTRACT: Fashion has merged and become one of the main interests for each individual and has a personal meaning according to the personality and taste preferences of each. This holds true for fashionable shoes as well, especially for ladies. Considering how it has evolved, footwear is one of the elements of fashion that reveals the social standing of its wearers. Shoes are no longer merely a basic necessity for human existence, but they are also now inextricably linked to the demands of fashion for the ideal image.

Women's shoes are created in a variety of styles that are characterized by model, color, and shape, whose purpose varies depending on the style they wish to exhibit, along with the evolution of fashion trends. Many women are on the lookout for new shoe improvements that are feminine but also straightforward and comfortable to wear. Privet is thus active as a company involved in fashion, specifically women's shoes, to meet the demands of the market. The company, which has been operating legally under the name CV. Privet Dwi Sentosa since October 23 2020, are produce the product made by local artisans with a variety of feminine models, however they still seem stylish and comfortable. Each Privet product is embellished with handmade features to give it a special, one-of-a-kind touch.

Considering the large opportunity in the market potential and the ability of local craftsmen to produce high-quality products, Privet wants to try to expand sales distribution by offering products directly to consumers by exploring direct-to-consumer promotion strategies based on the customer preferences like many other big brands do to attract the maximum market potential.

KEYWORDS: Customer Preference, Fashion, Local Craftsmen, Market Opportunity, Promotion Strategy.

INTRODUCTION

Fashion is something that everyone needs to pay attention to. Based on research conducted by Katadata (2021), the fashion category is ranked first as the most spent category by Indonesians. Indirectly, fashion has merged and become one of the main interests for each individual and has a personal meaning according to the personality and taste preferences of each. Everything must have been arranged taking into account the situation and the destination. Starting with the choice of clothing, colours, and materials, and moving on to the blending of hues and themes. This holds true for fashionable shoes as well, especially for ladies. Women frequently have to make a variety of decisions about what to wear and how to mix and match their outfits from head to toe. Unquestionably, one of the things that women need to pay attention to is footwear. Considering how it has evolved, footwear is one of the elements of fashion that reveals the social standing of its wearers. Shoes are no longer merely a basic necessity for human existence, but they are also now inextricably linked to the demands of fashion for the ideal image. Women's shoes are created in a variety of styles that are characterized by model, colour, and shape, whose purpose varies depending on the style they wish to exhibit, along with the evolution of fashion trends.

Figure 1. Most Spent Category by Indonesians, Katadata

Many women are on the lookout for new shoe improvements that are feminine but also straightforward and comfortable to wear. Privet is thus active as a company involved in fashion, specifically women's shoes, to meet the demands of the market. Privet collaborates with local craftsmen to create shoes with models and quality that are no less good than foreign-made or brand products. The guidance and empowerment of local craftsmen is carried out to encourage and participate directly in the #LocalPride movement. As a local brand that collaborates and interacts with many parties, of course there are many obstacles that occur in Privet. Privet as a business engaged in the women's footwear industry since 2018 has been selling by means of good cooperation with local stores in several major cities as well as local product distribution agencies from the government. From this, it can be concluded that the majority of sales made by Privet still depend on other businesses (B2B) or government (B2G). Considering the large market potential and the ability of local craftsmen to produce high-quality products, Privet wants to try to expand sales distribution by offering products directly to consumers by exploring direct-to-consumer promotion strategies like many other big brands do to attract the maximum market potential.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature review will explain about the theoretical foundation and the conceptual framework used for this research which discusses. This section will explain the data analysis of both internal (Value Proposition Design) and external (Porter's Five Force) as well as other analyses needed in this research.

Figure 2. Value Proposition Design, Osterwalder

Value Proposition Design or VPD is a reason why consumers should prefer our products over others. According to Osterwalder et al (2014), VPD is a tool that makes it easier to find a value proposition in a company's business model, and adjust it to the needs and desires of customers.

Figure 3. Porter's Five Forces, Kotler

Analyzing the rivalry within the industrial sector is one of the finest ways to spot potential company dangers and identify solutions to combat them. It will be easier to decide how to influence behavior and how this will affect outcomes, outcomes, and future planning if you are aware of the scale of the competition (Hole et al, 2019).

III. METHODOLOGY

Data collection will be carried out by bringing together internal data that the company already has, submitting interviews with internal parties and customers, as well as distributing questionnaires to consumers regarding their preferences on Privet's product. The data collected comes from the company's internal and some external data obtained from certain sources, such as: related literature, internal and external observation, previous studies that intersect with the research conducted, as well as other sources that come from outside the company's internal scope. Research will begin by collecting internal and external data to then be analyzed according to the research questions and adjusted to the objectives to be achieved. This research is based on a qualitative approach which is carried out by collecting primary data from internal companies as well as secondary data obtained through external analysis. Data collection will be carried out by bringing together internal data that the company already has, submitting interviews with internal parties and customers, as well as distributing questionnaires to consumers regarding their preferences on Privet's product. The data collected comes from the company's internal and some external data obtained from certain sources, such as: related literature, internal and external observation, previous studies that intersect with the research conducted, as well as other sources that come from outside the company's internal scope. This research activities will involve processing primary data gathered through observation and questionnaires. Observation is one of this research approaches for gathering data. According to earlier studies, systematic observation of the observed events is the procedure used to gather data and/or information. After that, options will be provided for the targeted respondents to choose from, and the questionnaires will be distributed, processed, and the analysis's findings will be drawn.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULT

The great opportunities that exist in the Indonesian women's footwear industry, makes Privet want to try to expand sales distribution by offering products directly to consumers by exploring direct-to-consumer promotion strategies like many other big brands do to attract the maximum market potential. Here's the following analysis to help Privet's exploration to gain maximum direct-sales market potential.

Value Proposition Design

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Value Proposition

- Product & Services

In the product & service section, as written is the value of the product or service offered to consumers. Privet is here as a local product in the form of handmade women's shoes with a feminine appearance and following trends.

- Gain Creators

Gain creators see how the products or services offered by Privet can benefit their consumers. Where products from Privet are handmade and pay great attention to the details of each process, then in the production process pay attention to quality, tidiness, and details, Privet also conducts research on trending fashion shoes and combines them with the original designs we have designed for each series.

- Pain Relievers

Pain relievers seek to reduce the risks in terms of losses that may be experienced by consumers. Privet can be found in person at several locations to make it easier for consumers to see our products in person. Privet also provides shoe care tutorials for each model issued to prevent errors in maintenance. Then Privet uses the "double sew" technique or repeated stitches in the process of sewing the shoes to the installation of the beads, as well as applying special glue in the layers of each shoe base, this aims to make the shoes more durable and stronger. Consumers can also make exchange systems or custom sizes if the shoe size does not match.

Customer Segment

- Customer Jobs

Customer jobs are part of the work done to meet the needs and what things are done by consumers in Privet, such as: Need to find comfortable shoes, looking for an online shop that offers women sandals/shoes, need to customize sandals/shoes sizes.

- Customer Gains

Customer gain is part of seeing the benefits that are expected and can be obtained by consumers. Privet products can be used by women who like a feminine style, equipped with cotton pads that make consumers more comfortable when using them.

- Customer Pain

Customer pain can see the negative side of financing that is not liked by consumers to the risks that consumers may get. There are Privet products whose material is not water-resistant, and the bead decoration or accessories may come off in certain cases.

Porter's Five Force

Understanding the competitive environment in which a product or service works can be done with the help of Porter's Five Forces Analysis. Knowing where competition comes from and how powerful each competitor is in the market might be helpful. The following are the analysis of this industry:

1. Threat of New Entrants

The risk of new competitors entering the Women's Shoes market is minimal. This is because there are many entrance obstacles, including the necessity for significant financial investments in machinery and equipment and the requirement to forge connections with suppliers and retailers. It is also difficult for newcomers to establish a presence on the market because a small number of big businesses control it and have well-known brands.

2. Bargaining Power of Buyers

In the market for women's shoes, purchasers have a fair amount of negotiating power. This is because there are numerous merchants and providers, which enables customers to compare prices and find the best offers. Additionally, shopping online allows customers access to a greater range of available goods. As a result, there is mounting pressure on producers to provide affordable pricing without sacrificing high quality and good design.

3. Bargaining Power of Suppliers

In the women's footwear sector, suppliers have limited negotiating strength. This is so that if the need arises, switching to a different supplier is simple due to the fact that many suppliers offer comparable goods and services. The bargaining leverage of suppliers is also diminished by the fact that many businesses are vertically integrated, which means they generate the majority of their raw materials.

4. Threat of Substitute Products

In the market for women's shoes, the threat of substitute products is rather minimal. This is because there aren't many good alternatives for shoes, which are a basic necessity. In addition, the fashionable nature of footwear makes it challenging for alternatives to compete, since consumers are more likely to stay shopping for footwear with the newest trend designs than alternative footwear items.

5. Competitive Rivalry

The rate of market competitiveness for women's shoes is pretty high. This is because there are many big businesses with well-known brands and a sizable number of tiny businesses attempting to break into the market with fresh ideas. Additionally, the fashion industry's nature necessitates constant innovation on the part of businesses in order to stay abreast of modern trends and customer's preferences.

After analysing both internal and external data, the following is the result of an exploration of promotional strategies opportunities that have been and will be carried out by Privet to achieve maximum market potential. Promotion mix is the greatest strategically put-together set of promotional components utilized to attain business objectives, claim Kotler and Keller (2016). These components serve as the marketing communicator's instruments for reaching out to customers. Because it will have a direct impact on boosting sales, promotion is a crucial and integral component of product marketing. Marketers must be able to provide information about the commercial products being sold to clients in terms of promotion. Promotional issues can take the shape of persuading, inviting, and reminding customers about the goods being supplied. Today's digital technology makes it simple to promote sales, leading many marketers to start using digital media to market their goods. This practice is frequently referred to as digital marketing. For internetsavvy business people, technology is employed to advertise products through social media or online markets. In terms of this research, Privet applies a promotion mix that focus on advertising to reach maximum market potential.

In marketing its products, Privet will always pay attention to the form of advertisements aimed at consumers. Privet plans to advertise on Instagram ads. The social media used can determine the target to be addressed specifically so that the advertising process will be more effective. In addition, the two media can also adjust the advertising budget and adjust the duration of the ad's display. The impact of each ad is also different, starting from increasing the number of followers, adding likes from posts, to increasing product sales. Privet focus to plans regular advertisements through Instagram ads with a budget of IDR 500,000 - 1,000,000 in total per month, this is intended to increase the intensity of advertisement appearances so that the product is better known by the wider community. In conducting advertisements through Instagram, Privet also pays attention to the content of the advertisements to be displayed, such as the design of attractive advertising campaigns on photo or video material.

Additionally, Privet test advertisements with conversion objectives, i.e., to show advertisements for product catalogue and determine the proportion of customers who make purchases. Here, Privet features promotional content that highlights products as well as special offers or discounts. It found out that the outcomes of the conversion goal ad experiments had a significant impact on Privet's ability to boost sales. Here, we give an advertising budget of IDR 60,000 along with the results attained from the ad, which reached 11,769 people. Of those, 98% were not followers of Privet Instagram, and the post has been viewed 13,605 times. According to the several advertising campaigns trials that Privet ran, each one had a varied effect on the intended audience.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis carried out, several promotional explorations were produced that could be implemented by Privet to increase interest and direct sales to consumers. First, by conducting regular advertisements on Privet social media platforms such as Instagram to attract potential target markets to be interested in and know about Privet products before finally making purchases. Then by spreading the Privet brand and products directly with the help of micro influencers which can have a direct impact on purchases.

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